

Synergizing Curative and Preventive Actions: Monthly Leprosy Summary

Report of Regional Director of Health Services Area- Colombo

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Background

Dermatology Clinics and Medical Officer of Health (MOH) field teams play mutually reinforcing roles in achieving early detection and sustained treatment outcomes.

Challenges identified:

- Delays in data transfer between clinic and field teams.
- Limited integration of clinic-based and community-level activities hindering timely follow up and contact screening.

To consolidate surveillance and operational data from dermatology clinics and MOH areas a standardized monthly reporting summary was developed and implemented since 01st of January 2025.

Description of the initiative

Clinic-level metrics include:

- Patient attendance and new case registrations.
- H544 form submissions.
- Defaulter follow-up actions.
- Contact screening outcomes.

Administrative processes documented:

- Filing of green copies at RDHS office.
- Dispatch of red copies to ALC.
- Updates to the district leprosy register.

MOH field-level activities monitored:

- Timely receipt of clinic notifications.
- Tracing of missing records.
- Effectiveness of contact screening.
- Referrals from MOH offices to dermatology clinics.

Monthly leprosy control summary for the month of () -2025
RDHS area- Colombo

1. Activities related to dermatology clinics

Clinic	Date visited	No of total patients as per patient files	MOH	No of new patients as per clinic leprosy register	No of H544 filled and sent to MOH areas	No of previous defaulters visited the clinic	No of follow up visits of already registered patients	No of contacts screened at clinic as per contact register	No of Green copies filed at RDHS office	Date and number of Red Copies sent to ALC	Date of completion of updating of district register

MOH area	Date/s visited and team members	No. of H544 on leprosy received as per notification register and institutions	Whether all notified cases from the dermatology clinics have been received by MOH office	If no, date of completion of tracing of missing records	No of screening of contacts done at MOH office	No of referrals of suspected patients made to dermatology clinics	No of diagnosed patients out of referred

Activities related to MOH areas

PHI (Leprosy Control) - CCP/RE.....

Figure 01

Methods Used for the Evaluation

This summary is used in review meetings at Colombo District.

Results

- ✓ Enhanced coordination between curative services and MOH field teams.
- ✓ Data reconciliation between curative and preventive sector to identify discrepancies.
- ✓ Since its inception earlier this year, this summary has been routinely forwarded to the Anti-Leprosy Campaign following its implementation.

Lessons Learnt

A consolidated summary report :

- Facilitate the integration of data from curative (clinic-based) and preventive (field-level) leprosy control activities.
- Potentially enabling streamlined data collection, timely reporting, coordination between clinical and field activities strengthening overall surveillance of leprosy.